

Supporting Information for “Tuning Water Networks via Ionic Liquid/Water Mixtures”

Archana Verma, John P. Stoppelman, and Jesse G. McDaniel*

School of Chemistry and Biochemistry,

Georgia Institute of Technology, Atlanta, Georgia 30332-0400

E-mail: mcdaniel@gatech.edu

1 Description of Analysis Methods

We elaborate on specific details of our analysis methods, specifically computing hydrogen bond histograms, trimer angle distribution functions, and percolation analysis. The NetworkX software was utilized to efficiently compute hydrogen bond histograms using the following protocol. For every saved frame in the simulation (1 ps intervals), a NetworkX graph object was created to represent the simulation frame. The graph is defined by adding “nodes” and “edges”; the oxygen atom of every water molecule is added as a unique node, and every hydrogen bond between water molecules is added as an edge connecting two nodes. Hydrogen bonds are defined by the criteria that the oxygen-oxygen distance between two water molecules is less than 0.36 nm, the O-H hydrogen bond distance is less than 0.245 nm, and the H-O-O angle is less than 30° . After the graph is created, the “degree” of each node is computed and histogrammed; the degree represents the number of adjacent nodes that a particular node is connected to, which in this case gives the number of hydrogen bonds. The degree distribution is normalized by the number of water molecules, giving the probability that a given water molecule exhibits a certain number of hydrogen bonds. This “per-frame” probability is then averaged over all frames of the simulation to give the final ensemble-averaged distribution shown in Figure 2, Figure S2, Figure S3, and Figure S4. Statistical uncertainty was estimated by dividing the total simulation into 5 blocks, and evaluating the standard deviation of the block averages; from this analysis, it is determined that any error bars would be smaller than the size of the plotted data symbols, and thus are not shown. These distributions are then “integrated” to give the average number of hydrogen bonds, as plotted in Figure 3. Note that comparison of Figure 3 and Figure S8 provides a nice consistency check, as Figure S8 computes the average number of hydrogen bonds utilizing a completely different method (e.g. integrating O-H RDFs).

The trimer angle distribution functions shown in Figure 4 were computed utilizing a similar approach. Water trimers were selected from each simulation frame, where a trimer is defined by three water molecules with one water molecule being within 0.36 nm (oxygen-

oxygen distance) of the other two water molecules; note that each water molecule may participate in one or more trimers, or none at all. Because the purpose is to analyze the trimer angle distribution, no subsequent criteria was imposed on the O-H distance or H-O-O angle to create the trimer histograms. The angle of the trimer is then histogrammed, and the histogram is normalized by the total number of trimers in each simulation frame, and then averaged over the number of simulation frames in the trajectory.

Percolation analysis shown in Figure 8 was conducted using the algorithm described by Edvinsson et al., *Mol. Simulat.* 1999, 23, 169-190, as implemented in an in-house Fortran code that is available upon request. Hydrogen bond networks were constructed with the analogous protocol as for the degree distributions, and then a recursive algorithm was used to search whether a continuous network exists that spanned the simulation box and was connected over its periodic image. If such a network exist, the frame was said to percolate and given a ‘1’. If not, the frame was given a ‘0’. The percolation probability, $R(\phi, V)$ was then computed by averaging these ‘1’s and ‘0’s over the simulation trajectory.

2 Rotational Correlation Functions of Water in IL/Water Mixtures

Rotational correlation functions for water in the IL/water mixtures are shown in Figure S1. The rotational correlation function is defined as

$$C(t) = \langle \mathbf{z}_{H_2O}(0) \cdot \mathbf{z}_{H_2O}(t) \rangle \tag{S1}$$

where \mathbf{z}_{H_2O} is the unit midbond vector between the two O-H bonds of a water molecule. The rotational correlation time, τ_1 , is defined by integrating the rotational correlation function, e.g.

$$\tau_1 = \int_0^{t_{max}} \langle \mathbf{z}_{H_2O}(0) \cdot \mathbf{z}_{H_2O}(t) \rangle dt \quad (\text{S2})$$

and we employ $t_{max} = 2$ ns in this work, which is a sufficient timescale for the correlation functions to decay to zero. The correlation times plotted in Figure 1 of the main manuscript are thus generated from integrating the correlation functions shown in Figure S1.

Figure S1: Rotational correlation function for water in IL/water mixtures as a function of water volume fraction for a) [BMIM⁺][BF₄⁻], b) [BMIM⁺][OTf⁻], c) [BMIM⁺][PF₆⁻], d) [BMIM⁺][TFSI⁻], and e) [BMIM⁺][NO₃⁻]. All simulations are at 300 K, except [BMIM⁺][NO₃⁻] / water mixtures which are at 320 K.

3 Hydrogen Bond Histograms for Water in [BMIM⁺][OTf⁻], [BMIM⁺][NO₃⁻], and [BMIM⁺][TFSI⁻] Water Mixtures

In Figures S2, S3, and S4, we show histograms of the number of hydrogen bonds per water molecule in [BMIM⁺][OTf⁻], [BMIM⁺][TFSI⁻], and [BMIM⁺][NO₃⁻] at varying water content. These graphs correspond to those shown for [BMIM⁺][BF₄⁻] and [BMIM⁺][PF₆⁻] in Figure 2 of the main manuscript. Next to the histograms are simulation snapshots for $\phi_{water}=0.08$ water volume fraction of the corresponding systems. In all figures, the hydrogen bond histogram of bulk water is plotted as a dashed line for reference.

Figure S2: Histograms of number of hydrogen bonds per water molecule for [BMIM⁺][OTf⁻] water mixtures of $0.02 \leq \phi_{water} \leq 0.25$ water volume fraction at 300K, and corresponding simulation snapshot for the $\phi_{water}=0.08$ water volume fraction system.

Figure S3: Histograms of number of hydrogen bonds per water molecule for $[\text{BMIM}^+][\text{TFSI}^-]$ water mixtures of $0.02 \leq \phi_{\text{water}} \leq 0.13$ water volume fraction at 300K, and corresponding simulation snapshot for the $\phi_{\text{water}}=0.08$ water volume fraction system.

Figure S4: Histograms of number of hydrogen bonds per water molecule for $[\text{BMIM}^+][\text{NO}_3^-]$ water mixtures of $0.02 \leq \phi_{\text{water}} \leq 0.25$ water volume fraction at 320K, and corresponding simulation snapshot for the $\phi_{\text{water}}=0.08$ water volume fraction system.

4 Simulation Snapshots of IL/Water Mixtures at 4% Water Content

In Figure S5 below, we show simulation snapshots of the IL/water systems at 4 % water by volume.

Figure S5: Simulation snapshots of IL/water mixtures at 4% water by volume for a) $[\text{BMIM}^+][\text{BF}_4^-]$, b) $[\text{BMIM}^+][\text{OTf}^-]$, c) $[\text{BMIM}^+][\text{PF}_6^-]$, d) $[\text{BMIM}^+][\text{TFSI}^-]$, and e) $[\text{BMIM}^+][\text{NO}_3^-]$.

5 Cluster Size Analysis

Water cluster size analysis was conducted utilizing the NetworkX software. We show two different metrics of water clustering within the IL/water systems. In Figure S6, we show a histogram of different sized water clusters in the IL/water mixtures at $\phi=0.08$ water volume fraction. Water clusters are defined by “graphs”, in which “nodes” are connected by “edges”, where the nodes are water molecules and an “edge” represents a close-contact interaction motif. We use two different definitions for edges; either 1) based on O-O close contact distance, or 2) hydrogen-bonding criteria that additionally involves evaluating O-H contact distance and H-O-O angle. In Figure S6, we utilize a criteria of O-O distance less than 0.36 nm to define edges (connections) between water molecules; this definition was chosen to facilitate connection with Figure 4 in the manuscript. In Figure S7, we show a “weight averaged cluster size” metric. This metric was computed using the hydrogen-bonding criteria (as discussed in the manuscript) to define the edges, in order to facilitate connection with Figures 2 and 3 of the manuscript. The weight averaged cluster size, $\langle n_w \rangle$, is defined as

$$\langle n_w \rangle = \sum_{n=1}^N n \left(\frac{nm_n}{N} \right) = \sum_{n=1}^N nW_n \quad (\text{S3})$$

here the sum is over clusters of different size, “n” denotes the number of water molecules in a cluster, “ m_n ” is the average number of clusters of size “n”, “ W_n ” denotes the weight fraction of water molecules that occupy clusters of size “n”, and “N” is the total number of water molecules in the system. Note that if instead the probability distribution is taken to be proportional to the number of clusters of a particular size “n”, e.g. $P_n \sim m_n/N$, then $n_w = \langle n^2 \rangle$ corresponds to a variance and thus reflects fluctuations in cluster size.

Figure S6: Histogram of water cluster sizes for $\phi=0.08$ water fraction IL/water mixtures. Clusters are defined by neighboring water molecules with O-O distance less than 0.36 nm.

Figure S7: Weight averaged cluster size “ $\langle n_w \rangle$ ” normalized by total number of water molecules “N”, computed for IL/water systems as a function of water volume fraction. Clusters are defined utilizing the hydrogen bonding criteria discussed in the manuscript.

6 Water Coordination Number

Water coordination numbers (N_{coord}) are computed by integrating the water-water pairwise distribution functions of Figure 5 in the main manuscript and Figure S9. We choose a cutoff distance of $r = 0.33\text{nm}$ which is just beyond the second peak in the water-water RDFs, and corresponds to the cutoff distance at which the coordination number of bulk water equals four. Therefore, N_{coord} computed at $r = 0.33\text{nm}$ provides an approximation for the number of hydrogen bonds of each water molecule. These values are shown in Figure S8 for the five IL/water mixtures. The data are consistent with the observed miscibility spectrum: $\text{PF}_6^-/(\text{CF}_3\text{SO}_2)_2\text{N}^-$, the hydrophobic systems have high coordination numbers, BF_4^- and NO_3^- have very low coordination numbers, and CF_3SO_3^- is an intermediate - though more similar in shape and value to the hydrophilic systems. This is consistent with the qualitative descriptions provided by the simulation snapshots: clusters will have a higher coordination number at a set shell distance (nearing the ideal limit 4) while a wire-like structure would approach a coordination number of two. We observe that the hydrophobic systems form clusters or high-coordination number groupings at higher water content. By contrast, even at the highest water content systems, the hydrophilic systems have coordination numbers at approximately 2, indicative of more wire-like structures.

Figure S8: Coordination Number (N_{coord}) of water molecules computed with a cutoff distance of 0.33 nm, and plotted for the five IL/water mixtures as a function of water content.

7 Pairwise Correlation Functions

In this section, we provide pairwise correlation functions supplementing those given in the main manuscript. In Figure S9, we show water-water pairwise distribution ($\rho g(r)$) for [BMIM⁺][NO₃⁻] / water mixtures. This Figure corresponds to the analogous plots in Figure 5 of the main manuscript for the four other IL/water mixtures.

In Figure S10, we show anion-anion pairwise distribution ($\rho g(r)$) for [BMIM⁺][TFSI⁻] / water mixtures. This distribution is computed using the center-of-mass of the anions, and corresponds to the analogous plots in Figure 7 of the main manuscript.

In Figure S11 we show anion-water pairwise distribution for [BMIM⁺][OTf⁻] and [BMIM⁺][TFSI⁻] / water mixtures, as computed using oxygen atoms of the anions and hydrogen atoms of water. The first peak around 0.2nm is consistent with typical hydrogen bond distance, and is in the same location in both systems. At distances greater than 1nm, the curved end behavior which results from water clustering is apparent in [BMIM⁺][TFSI⁻], but not [BMIM⁺][OTf⁻]

Figure S9: Pairwise probability distribution for water computed using oxygen-hydrogen distances for $[\text{BMIM}^+][\text{NO}_3^-]$ / water mixtures. The distribution is normalized by the density of water molecules.

Figure S10: Anion-anion pairwise distributions computed from anion center of mass for $[\text{BMIM}^+][\text{TFSI}^-]$ / water mixtures. Distributions are normalized by the density of anions.

Figure S11: Anion-water pairwise distribution computed from oxygen atoms of anion and hydrogen of water for (a) $[\text{BMIM}^+][\text{OTf}^-]$ (b) $[\text{BMIM}^+][\text{TFSI}^-]$ IL/water mixtures. Distributions are normalized by the density of water molecules.

In Figure S12 we show cation-water pairwise distribution for the five types of IL/water mixtures, as computed using the hydrogen atoms of the cation imidazolium ring, and oxygen atoms of water. The first peak in the distributions is at approximately 0.28 nm, which is somewhat larger than a typical hydrogen bond length. Secondary structures and end (> 1 nm) behavior are consistent with previous probability distributions, indicative of the relative water clustering degrees in the hydrophilic ($[\text{BMIM}^+][\text{BF}_4^-]$) and hydrophobic ($[\text{BMIM}^+][\text{PF}_6^-]$) systems.

Figure S12: Cation-water pairwise distribution computed from hydrogen atoms of the cation imidazolium ring and oxygen atoms of water for (a) $[\text{BMIM}^+][\text{BF}_4^-]$, (b) $[\text{BMIM}^+][\text{Otf}^-]$, (c) $[\text{BMIM}^+][\text{PF}_6^-]$, (d) $[\text{BMIM}^+][\text{TFSI}^-]$, and (e) $[\text{BMIM}^+][\text{NO}_3^-]$ IL/water mixtures. Distributions normalized by the density of water molecules.